

Forest bioenergy feedstock in Lithuania – Renewable energy goals and the use of forest resources

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ABSTRACT

Demands on forest bioenergy feedstock are expected to increase in many countries due to climate change mitigation. However, sustainable use of forest biomass resources can be ensured only if local and landscape conditions are taken into account, linking energy use to its resource base. The aim of this study was to analyse the forest biomass potential for Lithuania's energy pathways, while comparing the projected demand of forest bioenergy feedstock with resource projections. This was performed using the Landscape simulation and Ecological Assessment (LEcA) tool and the energy model MESSAGE. Biomass demand can be met up to 2050, after which demands under a Biomass Low pathway can still be met by the domestic forest resource if other wood uses are reduced, while Biomass High leads to a biomass deficit regarding domestic forest resources. Information exchange between the energy model and the LEcA tool enables an integrated sustainability assessment, and may contribute to a sustainable and efficient use of forest as a bioenergy feedstock resource.

1. Introduction

Forests play an important role for climate change mitigation by providing bioenergy feedstock to substitute fossil fuels, while they are also important for other ecosystem services such as providing industrial wood and carbon storage. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 7, Affordable and Clean Energy, aims to ensure access to sustainable energy for all, and to substantially increase the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix. To limit the increase in temperature to well below 2° Celsius according to the Paris Agreement, emissions of greenhouse gases worldwide need to be halved by 2050 and to be close to zero by 2100. To implement the Paris Agreement, in 2018, the European Commission adopted a long-term strategy entitled 'A clean planet for all', which presents a mid-century zero emissions strategy [1].

Renewable energy is overtaking fossil fuels as the largest source for energy supply and becoming the core to achieving the world's climate objectives [2]. Still, the other United Nations Sustainable Development Goals need to be reached simultaneously, such as Climate Action and Responsible Consumption and Production, which is why an integrated approach to sustainable use of resources is called for. However, there

are challenges, since increasing use of renewable energy sources (RES) such as forest bioenergy also means potential conflicts with other resource use and environmental goals. This may impact on their sustainability, which is one of the overarching policy challenges mentioned in SET-Plan Roadmap [3].

On an EU level, to combat climate change, the EU Renewable Energy Directive (2009/28/EC) aims to promote RES and to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in a sustainable way, ensuring that negative effects on ecosystem services are avoided [4,5]. A transition to a resource-efficient and low-carbon economy in Europe has been promoted [6], and in a bio-based economy, biomass is used not only for bioenergy purposes but also for materials [7]. Thus, it is essential to integrate multiple resource use and ecosystem services in assessments of policies and plans for increasing use of forest biomass as a RES. However, energy policy assessments seldom take landscape-level ecosystem services into account [8].

The country of Lithuania is forest-rich and out of the primary domestic energy resources, forest bioenergy currently accounts for 65.6%, and 16.9% of the gross inland consumption [9]. In the Lithuanian energy sector, forest biomass consumption for energy purposes has increased considerably. The bioenergy feedstock extraction almost

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doubled during the years 2000–2015, from 653.1 ktOE in 2000 to 1191.6 ktOE in 2015 [9]. This increase was mainly due to biomass consumption in the industry sector, and to district heating and electricity in the energy sector. Forest bioenergy feedstock is considered to have a high potential to remain one of the most important local renewable energy resources in the future.

In order to assess the sustainability of forest biomass use in energy pathways for Lithuania, methods and tools are needed that can link energy models with ecosystem services assessment tools for integrated resource analyses. This will allow for balancing various resource use and ecosystem services and analysing implications of forest bioenergy options. One such tool is the Landscape simulation and Ecological Assessment (LEcA) tool [10] where several ecosystem services can be assessed together in a GIS-based approach, including a sustainable production of forest bioenergy feedstock over a long time perspective.

This study aims to i) analyse the forest biomass potential for Lithuania using the LEcA tool, comparing it to energy pathways relying on forest bioenergy feedstock as a RES, and ii) discuss opportunities for information exchange between the energy model, in this case the MESSAGE model, and the LEcA tool, to find the potential for closer model integration in the future. This will enable the integration of relevant resource use and ecosystem services, including a sustainable production of forest bioenergy feedstock, in sustainability assessment of energy policy and related forest bioenergy options.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study area

The study area was the country of Lithuania (Fig. 1), where around 33.5% of the area is covered by forest [11]. The dominating tree species within the Lithuanian forest are pine (33.2%), birch (21.1%), and spruce (19.7%) [11]. Forest management went through major transformations after the restoration of independence in 1991, comprising the adoption of the Forest Law of the Republic of Lithuania [12]. This included turning towards a market economy, modernisation of forestry technologies, liberalisation of international trade, and acceptance of international environmental standards [13]. One of the key provisions of the new Forest Law was the introduction of four forest groups, defining the forest management regime for all forests within the group. These functional forest groups embrace *strict reserves*, where no active forest management is applied; *special purpose forests*, dedicated to encompass ecosystem protection and recreational use, with severe forest management restrictions; *protective forests* that are aimed at protection of soil or water, with some additional management restrictions compared to commercial forests; and *commercial forests* where timber production is prioritised [12] (Fig. 1).

2.2. Study design

An overview of the study design is presented in Fig. 2, where relationships and potential linkages between the energy model MESSAGE,

Fig. 1. The study area of Lithuania, illustrating the different forest management groups that are applied in the country (see text for explanation), urban areas (in purple) and roads (grey lines). Coordinate system LKS_1994_Lithuania_TM, spatial data from State Forest Survey Service (2016).

Fig. 2. Overview of the study design, with relationships and potential linking between the energy model MESSAGE with the LEcA tool, and with energy policy; see text for explanation.

the LEcA tool, and energy policy are illustrated. The pathways Biomass Low and Biomass High were run by the MESSAGE model for Lithuania. Exchange between the Biomass Low pathway and Lithuania energy policy has already been implemented [14]. Forest management strategies corresponding to these pathways were run using the LEcA tool. Then, in the LEcA tool, different allocation assumptions were applied concerning the proportion of wood used directly for energy, i.e. *firewood*. The arrow *a* illustrates the first comparison between outcomes. The blue arrows are possible linkages for future work, where the LEcA results could be fed back to the MESSAGE model and eventually also inform energy policy. The details of the study design are described in the following subsections.

2.3. The MESSAGE model and energy pathways

In order to estimate the cost optimal use of forest biomass for bioenergy purposes in Lithuania, a bottom up energy system model was run, created in the MESSAGE environment [15]. This linear programming model is focused on centralised heat and electricity supply, while other energy uses such as heat production in individual houses are modelled with less detail. Heat and electricity production is spatially disaggregated in the model to reflect isolated district heating systems. A wide variety of energy technologies (different types of heat plants and CHPs, technologies for electricity production, storage, etc.) is covered by the model. Also, considerable attention is paid to the reflection of existing and prospective policy measures, electricity exchange with foreign countries, and optimal allocation of reserve capacities. Variable energy resources (e.g. wind) availability is represented using probability curves. Following common energy modelling praxis, the MESSAGE model for Lithuania considers the cost optimal deployment of energy technologies, but does not consider other ecosystem services in stand-alone runs.

Using this model, the prospective biomass consumption for energy purposes under the two pathways Biomass Low and Biomass High was simulated. Both pathways represented the possible development of the Lithuanian energy sector, which correlates well with the current European Union energy policy. The Biomass Low pathway was originally derived from the analyses that were performed in the process of

preparation of the Lithuanian National Energy Strategy [14], while the Biomass High pathway was derived by slightly modifying Biomass Low in order to express a more intensive utilisation of forest bioenergy.

The energy policy of Lithuania was reflected in both pathways, being oriented towards the widest possible integration into the international energy markets and the optimal use of the country's energy infrastructure. The GDP growth rate was expected to be 3.5% until 2030, and 2.6% after 2030 (3.0% on average over the period from 2014 to 2050). The electricity demand during the period until 2050 was expected to grow on average by 1.7% annually (2.0% per year until 2030 and 1.5% per year after 2030) [14]. The Lithuanian economy would consume approximately 14.7 TW h of electricity in 2040, which means 5700 kW h per capita, corresponding to the current EU-28 countries average. The final energy demand growth rates would be much slower, an average of 0.6% per year [14]. The RES target expressed as its share of the final energy demand would be 30% in 2030 and 55% in 2050, which relates to the EU average in the corresponding year [16]. Both pathways represented the same energy policy conditions regarding the RES share in the final energy demand.

The pathways were based on common assumptions, except availability and price of biomass, see Table 1. In the Biomass Low pathway, the consumption of wood chips and wood waste was limited according to assumptions about their availability in the domestic market. This means that the total wood biomass availability for centralised energy generation purposes was constrained by 31.1 PJ (8.638 TW h) [14]. In the Biomass High pathway, the restrictions on biomass availability were absent, and it was allowed to import these products or to produce them locally, if there would be enough biomass resources available. In the Biomass High pathway the price of wood chips and wood waste was considerably cheaper than in the Biomass Low pathway. In the Biomass

Table 1
MESSAGE modelling assumptions concerning biomass availability and prices.

Pathway	Biomass Low	Biomass High
Price	High	Low
Biomass availability	Limited	Unlimited
Biomass consumption	Modelling result in MESSAGE	Modelling result in MESSAGE

High pathway the wood biomass prices corresponded to the current price level in Lithuania, which is in a range of 115–127 Euro/tonne (2.75–3.03 Euro/GJ) depending on wood biomass type. In the Biomass Low pathway, the wood biomass prices were 25–37% higher in 2017, compared to Biomass High. They were then increasing and in 2050 exceeded the Biomass High pathway prices by 100–125%.

The pathways for the future needs of forest bioenergy feedstock were run for Lithuania for the time period until 2065. Annual time steps were used in the time period 2011–2020, five-year time steps in the period until 2030, 10-year steps in the period until 2050, and one additional step reaching 2065. After 2050, the conditions were kept constant up to the final year 2115 to match the time line of the forest growth and management simulations, assuming that the EU targets for RES is intended to be kept in the decades following 2050 and that the total energy consumption remains constant.

2.4. The LECA tool

The LECA tool was developed for integrated sustainability assessment of forest ecosystem services [10], and contains linked modules embedded in a GIS framework. The modules used in this study were (i) the LandSim model that simulates forest growth and management, and (ii) the yield estimator that uses the spatially distributed output from LandSim to aggregate and estimate the yield of industrial wood and bioenergy feedstock (Fig. 2). The initial input data for the assessment was the Lithuanian State forest cadastre [17] and land use data [18] (Table 2). The LandSim model is constructed in the MatLab environment [19] while the other LECA modules are built and run using ArcGIS ModelBuilder [20].

Forest growth and management was simulated with the landscape simulator LandSim [21]. The forest development model at the core of the simulator is a matrix-based model of the Markov chain type, representing change by transition of areas (in this case, pixels) between fixed forest states. Management programmes can be specified, differentiating between site productivity, tree species, age, and volume. In simulations the activity probabilities can be shifted by a coefficient for a simulation period to meet, for example, a desired total harvest level. In the current study the landscape was represented by 25*25 m pixels. The state of each pixel of forest land was described by six variables, see Table 2.

The dynamic variables (mean age and standing volume) change during the simulations while the static variables (all other variables) remain as they were. Other land cover classes were not included in the forest simulations. For each pixel, changes of the class associations were projected in five-year time steps across the study area, from the base year 2015–2115. A simulation period of 100 years is useful for forest resource assessments, since it is necessary to cover the long-term dynamics of forest growth and management cycles. Activities such as clearcutting, thinning, and regeneration were simulated. The initial

forest description of the base year situation was derived from stand level data from the Lithuanian State forest cadastre [17], from which relevant attributes were used to create the LandSim variables.

In the simulations, transitions between classes of the dynamic variables for each pixel were projected by using transition probabilities based on data from the Lithuanian National Forest Inventory (NFI) permanent sample plot data [22]. The estimations were carried out using the Bayesian estimation functions from the European Forestry Dynamics Model package [23]. The initial activity probabilities for thinning and clearcutting were also estimated from the NFI data for the period 1998–2015 using logistic models with the variables above as predictor variables. Thus management specifications used in the simulations represented a business-as-usual (BAU) strategy, representing forest management that has been applied in Lithuania during this period.

As a response to the results of Strategy BAU, and the higher demands of biomass quantities of the MESSAGE pathway Biomass High, a second forest management strategy was created, Strategy INT, in which a more intensive forest management was applied in order to increase the harvests. This was done by increasing the probabilities of harvesting, which lowered the mean final harvest age for all categories of forests. Still, also in Strategy INT the mean final harvest age was higher than the minimum legal final harvest age, which ultimately regulates how much wood can be harvested. The outputs from LandSim were used for estimation of the development of the provision of industrial wood and forest bioenergy feedstock.

2.5. Forest bioenergy feedstock

Current technological processes in forest harvesting and wood processing create several distinct types of forest bioenergy feedstock. Firstly, the harvested stemwood can be consumed for fuel directly, for example, as solid-piece *firewood*. This is primarily stemwood that has no alternative material use due to technical quality flaws (too small dimensions, rot, and form defects), but secondarily it could be some fraction of the industrial wood (otherwise used in construction, for sawmilling, veneer production, particle board production or as pulpwood). Secondly, the proportion of industrial wood from the harvested stemwood affects the amounts of produced *industrial waste* (sawdust, wood chips and pulpmilling by-products). Thirdly, left in the forest are the *logging residues* (tops, branches and stumps) that could be collected and used. Lastly, there is the *recycled wood* that comes from demolishing old constructions, recycling furniture, wooden packaging etc. Therefore, forest bioenergy feedstock and industrial wood are closely linked resources that need to be assessed together.

Using the LECA tool, harvested stem volume was derived for each time step (Fig. 2). From these records, forest bioenergy feedstock yields covering the categories *fire wood*, *industrial waste* and *logging residues* were estimated, see Tables 3 and 4. Recycled wood was not considered

Table 2
Input and output parameters used in the simulation of forest growth and management by the LECA tool.

Input parameters (base year)			
	Type	Number of classes	Description
Age	Dynamic	33	Mean age of forest stand in five-year classes
Volume	Dynamic	13	Standing volume (stems) in forest with bark
Tree species	Static	8	Dominating tree species (> 50% of standing volume)
Productivity	Static	2	Site productivity
Ownership	Static	2	Ownership
Forest group	Static	4	Forest group related to management strategy
Output parameters (five-year time steps for 100 years)			
Firewood			Volume (roundwood) with bark, and energy content
Industrial wood			Volume (roundwood) with bark, and energy content
Industrial waste wood			Volume (chips and sawdust), and energy content
Harvest residues			Volume (chips), and energy content

Table 3

Volume expansion factors (VEF) for estimating the volume of harvest residues that could be extracted without negative environmental impacts; a) branches and tops, and b) stumps; based on the harvested stem volume (State Forest Service, 2010).

a) Branches and tops	Dominating tree species							
	Pine	Spruce	Birch	Aspen	Black alder	Grey alder	Oak	Ash
Soil type	Additional % of harvested stem volume: branches and tops							
VEF1: steep, poor eroded, organic poor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
VEF2: dry poor, moist poor, organic eroded	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	3
VEF3: dry with some fertility	10	12	12	10	10	10	10	10
VEF4: dry with high fertility	12	15	14	12	10	10	13	15
b) Stumps	Dominating tree species							
	Pine	Spruce	Birch	Aspen	Black alder	Grey alder	Oak	Ash
Soil type	Additional % of harvested stem volume: stumps							
VEF1: steep, poor eroded, organic poor	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
VEF2: dry poor, moist poor, organic eroded	4	4	3	4	3	3	4	3
VEF3: dry with some fertility	14	14	10	13	10	10	12	10
VEF4: dry with high fertility	21	21	15	15	15	14	17	16

in this study. Harvestable *logging residues* were considered as those that could be extracted while minimising soil-related damage to forest ecosystems (Table 3), according to Lithuanian forest legislation [24]. These environmental restrictions involve 1) poor soils, where the objective is to maintain the natural fertility; 2) for soils with a slope of more than 15°, remaining cutting residues are supposed to make such soils stable; 3) for eroded soils, the aim is to minimize the erosion process; 4) for moist soils, the objective is to minimize the damage on the soils; and 5) for organic soils, extraction is not allowed due to both damage avoidance and maintaining the property [24].

The industrial wood was derived from the harvested stem volume after subtracting the amount that was used for firewood. For simplicity we divided all industrial wood into only two categories: sawlogs and pulpwood. Other material uses such as veneer production or direct use in construction are currently small in Lithuania. Particle board logs were merged into the pulpwood category because none of these creates substantial amounts of industrial waste within Lithuania; the former due to the characteristics of the production technology, and the latter due to the fact that it is exported for processing outside the country.

Since harvested stemwood can be used in different ways, assumptions had to be made about allocation between these (Table 4). In industrialised countries firewood is often the economically least valuable wood assortment. However, policy measures and local economic circumstances might lead to a different allocation of the harvested stemwood, including higher proportions of firewood. Following these considerations we made assumptions regarding the use of harvested stemwood (Table 4), based on wood balance statistics from the Lithuanian State Forest Service [25,26]. The amount of wood reported to be used as firewood according to these statistics exceeds the amount of technical firewood (not suitable for material uses according to quality standards [25,26]) by 26% (in relation to the total harvest). The way these data were derived was that all wood that was not reported as

processed by any of the processing facilities in Lithuania was considered as used for energy generation. Given certain ambiguity of these data, we decided to use two sets of assumptions: Assumption A where the proportion of firewood was set to 20% as determined by technical wood quality, and Assumption B where this proportion was set to 46% as reported to be used as firewood in the statistics (Table 4). In addition, we tested a flexible approach, Assumption FLEX, where we increased the proportion of firewood to meet the bioenergy demand, by decreasing firstly the supply for pulpwood and, if more was needed, also sawlogs were used as firewood.

3. Results

3.1. Energy pathways

The results from the energy pathways Biomass Low and Biomass High, projecting the use of forest bioenergy feedstock as a RES, are shown in Fig. 3. For the year 2015 (the starting year for the LECA simulations), a use of 13.813 TWh was projected in Biomass Low and 13.873 TWh in Biomass High. As can be seen in the figure, later on in year 2050 the Biomass Low pathway projected the use to reach 20.786 TWh, and 31.365 TWh in Biomass High. After 2050, the last year with MESSAGE results, the use of biomass in both pathways was considered to keep the same level as those in year 2050. On average for the whole projected period of 100 years, the bioenergy use per year was 17.114 TWh in the Biomass Low pathway and 23.029 TWh in Biomass High.

The RES target in the MESSAGE model runs was set as the RES share in the final energy demand. This share was the same for both pathways and increased from the current level up to 55% in 2050. However, the assumed RES target in final energy, from the optimisation results converted into RES shares of the primary energy, differed slightly between

Table 4

Assumptions concerning the use of harvested stemwood and harvest residues for bioenergy purposes (State Forest Service, 2010; State Forest Service 2015a).

Amount related to the total harvested volume	Assumption A	Assumption B	Assumption FLEX
Industrial waste ^a from extracted roundwood volume with bark	33%	20%	0–20% ^b
Firewood from extracted roundwood volume with bark	20%	46%	0–100%
Additional volumes of logging residues (branches and tops), see Table 3	0–15%	0–15%	0–15%
Additional volumes of logging residues (stumps), see Table 3	0–21%	0–21%	0–21%

^a Solid wood equivalent.

^b Depending on demanded amounts for energy use; maximum level for industrial waste is based on the current proportion of the total of actually used sawlogs from the total amount of extracted roundwood [25].

Fig. 3. Forest biomass demand for bioenergy feedstock as modelled by the MESSAGE energy model, from 2015 up to 2050, in the Biomass High and Biomass Low pathways. The vertical dotted line shows where the MESSAGE results end and the assumptions of a continued high use of forest biomass start. This figure also shows a comparison of these pathways with the supply according to the LECA tool estimations under the two forest management strategies BAU and INT.

the Biomass Low and Biomass High pathways. These differences were caused by the different technological structure of the energy sector in the analysed pathways, and accordingly by the different overall efficiency of the energy conversion from primary to final energy. The RES target as its share of primary energy in the Biomass Low pathway would be 56.8% in year 2050, which however was not achieved. It would be necessary to consume an additional 5.245 TWh of RES in order to reach this target. In the Biomass High pathway the RES share target in 2050 would be 59.7% (in primary energy). This was achieved in the calculations because the upper limit on the forest biomass quantity that is available for energy feedstock production purposes [14] was not applied.

3.2. Forest bioenergy feedstock

The total forest bioenergy feedstock of different types that could be extracted according to the LECA simulations of the BAU and INT forest management strategies is illustrated in Fig. 4. As can be seen, there were substantial differences in the results, depending not only on forest management strategy, but on the assumptions that were made concerning use of forest biomass compartments for bioenergy purposes. Strategy INT resulted in around 9.5% higher overall yield within the period 2016–2050, compared to Strategy BAU. However, when applying Strategy INT over the whole 100-year period, the increase in overall yield was only 1.2%.

With Strategy INT, the harvest was very high in the beginning of the simulation period, but stabilised and then decreased after around year 2040, to become even lower than with Strategy BAU (Figs. 3 and 4) as a consequence of the extensive early cuttings. This pattern was due to the initial state of the forest, combined with the effect that the intensive cuttings in the early periods had on the overall age class structure of the forest, leading to a lack of harvestable forests later on. Strategy INT featured a slightly higher average net growth (6.27 vs 6.24 m³/

year*ha), which was caused by the more optimal rotations applied later in the simulation and the initial removal of the slower growing old forests. On average, the proportion of the utilised net growth in both strategies was between 91 and 92%. This represents a significant increase compared to the roughly 65–70% that are characteristic of current Lithuanian forestry.

The supply of *firewood* with Assumption A and Strategy BAU for the first simulated period 2016–2020 was 1.57 Mm³ per year, which by 2050 increased to 2.21 Mm³, and then slightly decreased, with a yearly average of 2.00 Mm³ over the whole period of 100 years (Fig. 4). With Strategy INT it was 2.21 Mm³ in the first period, 2.14 Mm³ by 2050, and it slightly increased at the end of the period, with almost the same yearly average of 2.02 Mm³ over the whole period. In contrast, the supply of *firewood* with Assumption B and Strategy BAU for the first period 2016–2020 was 4.12 Mm³ per year, which by 2050 increased to 5.80 Mm³, and then slightly decreased, with a yearly average of 5.24 Mm³ over the whole period. With Strategy INT it was 5.80 Mm³ in the first period, 5.63 Mm³ by 2050, and it slightly increased at the end of the period, with a yearly average of 5.30 Mm³ over the whole period.

The estimate of *industrial waste* with Assumption A and Strategy BAU for the first period 2016–2020 was 2.59 Mm³ per year, which by 2050 increased to 3.64 Mm³ and then decreased, with a yearly average of 3.29 Mm³ over the whole simulated period of 100 years (Fig. 4). With Strategy INT it was 3.64 Mm³ in the first period, 3.54 Mm³ by 2050 and it slightly increased at the end of the period, with a yearly average of 3.33 Mm³ over the whole period. However, the estimate of *industrial wood* with Assumption B and Strategy BAU for the first period was 1.57 Mm³ per year, which by 2050 increased to 2.21 Mm³ and then slightly decreased, with a yearly average of 2.00 Mm³ over the whole period. With Strategy INT it was 2.21 Mm³ in the first period, 2.14 Mm³ by 2050, and it slightly increased at the end of the period, with a yearly average of 2.02 Mm³ over the whole period.

Fig. 4 also shows the *logging residues* that could be extracted

Fig. 4. The total forest bioenergy feedstock that could be extracted according to the LECA estimations for the forest management strategies BAU and INT, applying Assumption A and B concerning use of harvested stemwood.

according to the two simulated management strategies. The estimate with Strategy BAU for the first period was 2.42 Mm³ per year, which by 2050 increased to 3.25 Mm³ and then decreased, with a yearly average of 2.94 Mm³ over the whole period. With Strategy INT it instead started on a high level, 3.40 Mm³ per year in the first period, then decreased to 3.16 Mm³ by 2050, and then slightly decreased even more, with a yearly average of 2.98 Mm³ over the whole period.

3.3. Comparison of the results between models

The projected forest biomass use in the energy pathways Biomass Low, compared to the total resource availability that was estimated by the LECA tool, is illustrated in Fig. 3. On average over the whole period (2015–2115), the total available forest biomass resource with Assumption A, applying the BAU and INT management strategies, covered 102% and 104% of the projected use, respectively (without stumps 81% and 82%). By contrast, with Assumption B it covered 126% and 128% of the projected use, respectively (without stumps 105% and 107%). So, with both management strategies and both assumptions, the projected use of forest bioenergy feedstock could be seen as covered when looking at the whole period, especially with Assumption B. With Assumption A, while showing a surplus in the early decades, the later parts of the simulation period would though show a shortage in relation to the projected use.

The bioenergy feedstock use in the Biomass High pathway was not equally well covered (Fig. 3). On average over the whole period (2015–2115), the total forest biomass supply with Assumption A, applying the BAU and INT management strategies, covered 72% and 73%

of the projected use, respectively (without stumps 57% and 58%). On the other hand, with Assumption B it covered 89% and 90%, respectively (without stumps 74% and 75%). So, with both forest management strategies and both assumptions, the biomass use in the Biomass High pathway can hardly be fulfilled in the long run, especially after 2050 as projected by the LECA tool (Fig. 3).

In order to illustrate the relationship between the projected biomass use in the energy pathways and the projected stemwood harvest levels we introduced Assumption FLEX, implying variable proportions of wood uses, as opposed to the fixed Assumption sets A and B (Fig. 5). This means that firewood use was prioritised above all other uses (first above pulpwood, then sawlogs) and its proportion was raised until the projected biomass use for energy was met. When even 100% firewood was not enough to meet the biomass demand, the deficit in % of the total projected wood extraction in the given period was recorded. The shifts in the allocation of stemwood harvest did not affect the amounts of extracted logging residues and stumps.

The proportion of firewood was initially around 20% and changed little until 2050 in all combinations (Fig. 5). However, after 2050 the differences between the energy pathways were very distinct. For Biomass Low, regardless of the forest management strategy, the highest proportion of firewood would be around 40%, while most of the time steps between 30 and 40%. In contrast, in the Biomass High combined with Strategy BAU the required proportion of firewood would increase to around 80% and by 2080 would be 100% and producing a deficit of 1–2%. Combined with Strategy INT the pattern would be even more drastic with a firewood requirement of 100% already by 2065 and the deficit reaching 5–6%. This was caused by the simultaneous sharp

Fig. 5. Required utilisation of harvested stemwood in order to meet the bioenergy feedstock demand (Assumption FLEX) in the energy pathways Biomass Low and Biomass High, with the forest management strategies BAU and INT.

increase of the demand for biomass and the dip in the harvest levels in the second half of the simulation period characteristic for Strategy INT.

4. Discussion

For Lithuania, the supply of forest bioenergy feedstock matched the projected demand of the Biomass Low pathway relatively well under both forest management strategies if stump extraction was included (Figs. 3 and 4). Without extracting stumps, the Biomass Low demand could only be met applying Assumption B. However, there was also a large gap between the projected biomass demand of the Biomass High pathway and the projected supply with Strategy INT. Even with an assumption of 100% utilisation of roundwood for energy, this energy pathway could not be supported consistently throughout the entire simulation period (Fig. 5).

The total supply of forest bioenergy feedstock with Strategy INT was substantially higher in the early periods of the LEcA simulations, compared to Strategy BAU, but would have predictable drawbacks in the long run (Fig. 3). This illustrates the need for a long-term simulation period for forest systems, where ending at year 2050 might not show the whole picture. However, with long-term simulation comes increasing uncertainties, and other factors like climate change may need to be taken into account. Climate change could potentially lead to increasing yields but also higher risks for storm-felling, droughts and flooding. Another problem with intensified forestry is the increased harvest of mature and old forest, and overall higher use of the net growth, which may lead to impacts on carbon storage, biodiversity and recreation values of the forest [10].

In the assessment of forest bioenergy feedstock with the LEcA tool, the assumptions regarding use of different biomass compartments highly influenced the results (Figs. 3 and 4). Assumption A (*technical standards*) and B (*reported use*) of harvested stemwood was based on the wood balance data [25,26]. Since it is a business-as-usual forest management strategy, for Strategy BAU it could be interesting to compare with another type of empirical data; the statistical yearbook of forestry [11]. According to this source, the proportion of *firewood* as of 2015 would be 31% (2.1 of the 6.7 Mm³), which is somewhere in between our Assumptions A and B. Thus, the empirical data is ambiguous and our results could therefore be seen as a range, indicating the possible development of the forest bioenergy feedstock of Lithuania.

In order to compare the estimates of *logging residues* with the statistical yearbook of forestry for 2015 [11], only tops and branches can be considered since stumps are currently not extracted in Lithuania. According to this source, the realised bioenergy feedstock from logging residues accounted for 0.4 Mm³ in year 2015. In comparison, the corresponding LEcA estimate with Strategy BAU for 2016–2020 was 1.03 Mm³ tops and branches per year. Thus our results indicate a substantial unrealised potential for increased extraction of harvest residues. However, impacts on ecosystem functions could be anticipated with extensive use of logging residues, for instance on the long-term forest productivity, leakage of toxic substances, and biodiversity (e.g. Ref. [27]). The restriction preventing soil damage on moist soils that was applied in our assessment may be the most significant when it comes to the amount of residues that would be available for harvest. It is not clear, though, to what extent the applied restrictions would suffice to counteract other impacts on forest ecosystems. Therefore,

additional restrictions might be necessary in order to protect the long-term sustainability of forest ecosystems.

Transport distance is another restriction that might need to be considered. The transport distance from harvesting sites to CHP plants might affect both economy and climate impacts [28–32]. This issue has been studied for Lithuania [33] and could be addressed in more detailed studies of forest bioenergy feedstock supply. Finally, it should be kept in mind that logging residue extraction, even at its maximum, can contribute to the total forest biomass supply only by some 15% under the Biomass Low pathway and, understandably, even less under Biomass High. Noteworthy, the stumps, currently not extracted at all, can contribute with at least as much biomass as the tree tops and branches.

4.1. Energy pathways and the supply of forest resources

Within the energy pathways (Fig. 3), there is a steep increase in biomass consumption between 2040 and 2050. This can be explained by the RES targets aligned with the EU Energy Roadmap [16], along with a gradual increase of energy demand and a changing technology structure due to the end of their lifetime, which makes new investments in energy generation from biomass more attractive. This biomass consumption growth trend is common for both pathways, but the scale is different due to higher biomass consumption in the Biomass High pathway. After this steep increase and implementation of EU and national policy, the situation is projected to be very different than in the earlier years. As mentioned, the demands of Biomass Low may be met relatively well, under certain assumptions, while Biomass High is projected to lead to a substantial deficit.

In the assessment, we focused primarily on firewood, industrial waste, and logging residues. An increased demand for forest bioenergy feedstock could be expected to increase the extraction of harvest residues, possibly also stumps. In addition, to some extent industrial wood would be considered as an alternative source when the other sources are exhausted. In order to explore and illustrate the balance between bioenergy feedstock and industrial wood, we show the required utilisation of harvested stemwood in order to meet the demand in the energy pathways (Fig. 5). Here, we can see how this competition would evolve if bioenergy was the first choice for allocation of harvested stemwood. First, *technical firewood* is used, and when exhausted, assortments suitable for pulpwood are used, and after that sawlogs (Assumption FLEX). In both pathways, industrial wood is used to different extents from 2050 and thereafter, and in Biomass High, all industrial wood is required as firewood and still a deficit is expected.

So, at higher levels of demand, competition for raw material is expected to occur between the bioenergy sector and the wood board industry, as well as the pulp and paper producers [34–37]. However, the extent to which industrial wood might be used for bioenergy purposes is very difficult to predict, and it may require quite strong price increases to divert wood flows from industrial uses to energy use (e.g. Ref. [38]). Moreover, the overall demand for wood can also be foreseen to increase in a transition to a green economy where wood is a renewable material used on a large scale to substitute, for example, fossil-based products [7]. This competition has been addressed in studies of cascading use, where the main idea is to use forest biomass as materials first, and the second choice would be bioenergy purposes [39,40]. From these perspectives, our results suggest that the ambitious levels of use of forest bioenergy feedstock for Lithuania may be too high, especially in the Biomass High pathway, which will not be sustainable in the long run if domestic sources are targeted.

4.2. Integrated sustainability assessment

The LEcA tool builds on a GIS-based approach to the bioenergy feedstock problem, using data that in this context has a high geographical resolution. This gives more detailed and localised information than what would be possible in more aggregated approaches. Other

studies that use GIS-based approaches take into account the spatial variability of biomass resources as well as transport networks to find suitable siting of biomass power plants (e.g. Refs. [31,41–44]). By contrast, the LEcA tool can assess the sustainability of using existing or planned biomass power plants and the current forest state, simulating future development of this resource under alternative policies and management strategies. In addition, the economic perspective with a geographic dimension can be further developed using GIS-based methods, similar to Ref. [45].

The availability of forest biomass for bioenergy feedstock is a crucial part of the energy policy of a forest-rich country, in view of the climate goals and targets for renewable energy. Several ways to reach these goals can be assessed using the LEcA tool, where the options and their sustainability can be highlighted. In order to widen the set of forest bioenergy options for Lithuania, the forest simulations can be re-run with the LandSim module with alternative management options. LandSim can simulate forest growth and management using a minimum of forest data compared to conventional tools used for forest management planning (e.g. Ref. [46]). Due to the modest data requirements, it allows for exploring forest management strategies across the whole landscape [21].

The results can be fed back to the energy assessment model for informed adjustments concerning a sustainable production of forest bioenergy feedstock. In the Biomass Low pathway, the consumption of industrial waste was limited according to assumptions about their availability in the domestic market, and these assumptions could be informed by the LEcA estimates for the actual period. This information could be fed back to the MESSAGE model, advising an adjustment of the domestic availability (Fig. 3). In addition, in the LEcA simulations of forest management, the activity probabilities can be shifted by a coefficient for an individual simulation period (instead of, as in the current study, for the whole period) to meet a desired total harvest level. When a set of suitable forest management strategies is found, the implications for ecosystem services can be assessed using the LEcA tool. The output can then be used to inform energy policy about the long-term sustainability of alternative bioenergy options.

5. Conclusions

The comparison between the energy pathways and the LEcA tool simulations allowed for new insights on the relationship between supply and demand for forest bioenergy feedstock for Lithuania. With the Biomass Low pathway, the biomass supply would suffice during the first decades up to the year 2050. However, after that the outcomes would depend on the use of harvested stemwood for industrial wood or bioenergy purposes. In addition, stumps would have to be used during this period in order to meet the demand. By contrast, with the Biomass High pathway, the biomass supply would mainly meet the demand up to year 2050, with a possible shortage during the first period. But after that, the projected biomass use would be so high that there would be a deficit, even in the unlikely case that eventually all harvested stemwood was used for bioenergy purposes. Therefore, it can be concluded that the ambitions of the energy policy to use forest bioenergy feedstock may be too high to be sustainable, and could therefore be reconsidered, especially for the Biomass High pathway.

The joint application of the LEcA tool, applying a GIS-based approach, and the energy model MESSAGE in the frame of one study enabled the information exchange between a national-level energy model and an assessment with landscape-level resolution of local resources and ecosystem services. Information from the energy model influenced the forest management strategy, and more synchronised information about demand for forest biomass could be used to modify forest management and the assumed use of forest biomass compartments in order to reach certain levels of bioenergy feedstock extraction. In addition, the projected supply of forest biomass can inform the assumptions of the energy model for different time steps. This information

exchange between the energy model and the LECA tool will enable an integrated sustainability assessment of resource use and ecosystem services, promoting a sustainable and efficient use of forest biomass as a bioenergy feedstock resource.

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